

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) LUT_BZFP

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: LUT_BZFP

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0031 Å	Wavelength=1.54184	
Cell:	a=12.1123 (6)	b=13.4556 (7)	c=19.5065 (12)
	alpha=90	beta=94.760 (6)	gamma=90
Temperature:	293 K		
	Calculated	Reported	
Volume	3168.2 (3)	3168.2 (3)	
Space group	P 21/c	P 21/c	
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc	
Moiety formula	C15 H10 O6, 2 (C13 H9 N O)	C15 H10 O6, 2 (C13 H9 N O)	
Sum formula	C41 H28 N2 O8	C41 H28 N2 O8	
Mr	676.65	676.65	
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.419	1.419	
Z	4	4	
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.818	0.818	
F000	1408.0	1408.0	
F000'	1412.59		
h, k, lmax	15, 16, 24	15, 16, 24	
Nref	6614	6458	
Tmin, Tmax	0.822, 0.944	0.854, 1.000	
Tmin'	0.751		

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.854 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 0.976

Theta(max)= 76.030

R(reflections)= 0.0496(4598)

wR2(reflections)=
0.1489(6458)

S = 1.027

Npar= 460

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT250_ALERT_2_C	Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i,j)> Tensor(Resd	1)	2.3	Note
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C	Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i,j)> Tensor(Resd	3)	2.2	Note
PLAT355_ALERT_3_C	Long O-H (X0.82,N0.98A) O3P - H3PO	.	1.01	Ang.
PLAT355_ALERT_3_C	Long O-H (X0.82,N0.98A) O5 - H5O	.	1.05	Ang.
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance	5.490	Check
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L=	0.600	5	Report
	0 12 1, 0 11 3, -1 12 3, -1 11 7, 3 7 18,			
PLAT918_ALERT_3_C	Reflection(s) with I(obs) much Smaller I(calc)	.	1	Check
	0 4 1,			

● **Alert level G**

PLAT007_ALERT_5_G	Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms	4	Report
	H3PO H4PO H5O H7O			
PLAT199_ALERT_1_G	Reported _cell_measurement_temperature (K)	293	Check
PLAT200_ALERT_1_G	Reported _diffn_ambient_temperature (K)	293	Check
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O11	.	105.5	Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O11A	.	105.4	Degree
PLAT480_ALERT_4_G	Long H...A H-Bond Reported H3	..04	2.61	Ang.
PLAT480_ALERT_4_G	Long H...A H-Bond Reported H13A	..03P	2.64	Ang.
PLAT480_ALERT_4_G	Long H...A H-Bond Reported H18A	..04	2.63	Ang.
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G	Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels	2	Note
	H3PO H4PO			
PLAT899_ALERT_4_G	SHELXL2018 is Outdated and Succeeded by SHELXL		2019/3	Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L=	0.600	151	Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G	Number of HKL-OMIT Records in Embedded .res File		4	Note
	0 12 1, -1 12 3, 0 11 3, -1 11 7,			
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G	Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity	2.1	Low
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G	The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value	5.170	Note
	Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 2.88 or SHELX Weight 14.50			Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.		4	Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
7 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
15 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

2 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data

6 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
6 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
6 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
2 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

PLATON version of 23/04/2026; check.def file version of 30/03/2026

duplicate check

No duplication found
